

A SOCIOCULTURAL PHENOMENON

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Annotation: The most stable and visible subcultural formations today are those represented by young people. The phenomenon of youth subculture is a fairly new phenomenon in the history of mankind. Researchers involved in youth issues associate the emergence of this phenomenon with the separation of the youth of Europe and the United States in the 20th century into a special social stratum. The reason for this was the beginning of the industrial revolution, which significantly increased the transition period from childhood to adulthood.

Key words: phenomenon, traditional culture, adults, adolescence, youth culture, adulthood, slang, linguistic personality, general slang, special slang.

Traditional culture was characterized by a direct transition from childhood to adulthood: "having left the guardianship of women, the child was thrown into the exhausting rural labor or military training ..., precocity was common in primitive societies". The constitution of a technogenic civilization entailed a complication of the division of labor and production processes and, thus, caused the need to increase the time for education and professional training in adolescence. Such changes in production activities significantly lengthened the period of socialization of young people into the world of adults and contributed to their separation into one of the relatively new and most dynamically developing socio-cultural systems of society.

The allocation of youth into a separate socio-demographic group requires the definition of its highest and lowest age limits, as well as the identification of other important systematizing qualities inherent in it, which are social qualities, psychological features and cultural characteristics. When determining the boundaries of youth age, researchers traditionally start from the physiological and psychological characteristics of this period. Social characteristics are also often cited as determinants. The choice of certain features and characteristics that serve to designate youth and distinguish it from other groups of society depends on the specific sciences, the object of study of which it is: biology, psychology, demography, sociology, pedagogy, sociolinguistics, etc. In accordance with this, the boundaries of the youth age are narrowing or expanding. It should be noted that the biological and psychological concepts consider young people rather narrowly, limiting themselves to the concept of

“adolescence” and the physiological and psychological changes associated with it: the process of puberty, inclusive, up to the period of relative cessation of the accelerated growth of the body, as well as the restructuring of the basic personality structures - the disintegration of childhood traits and the formation of relatively well-defined stable traits of character and behavior. With this understanding, adolescence is limited to the age from 13-14 years old to 20-21 years old. As for social science, it is characterized by a comprehensive understanding of youth as a subject of society, a system of reproduction and production in the aggregate of its social characteristics and problems. Youth in sociology acts as a social group that emerged as a result of the industrialization of society. The lower limit of youth age - adolescence, sociologists (like other scientists) associate with puberty, graduation from secondary school and the beginning of vocational training. When determining the upper limit, social characteristics are predominantly decisive in sociology, namely: the end of vocational training, the achievement of economic independence from parents, the fulfillment of “adult” roles in society, marriage, etc. From the standpoint of both Western and domestic sociology, on average, the age limits of the concept of “youth” lie in the range from 14-15 to 29-31 years.

The above facts show that the concept “youth culture” covers fairly wide age borders, uniting both adolescents and people of youthful age. A similar distinction is presented in the works of Western sociologists who identified these two age groups terms adolescence and youth. The selection of adolescence Western scientists attribute to the famous psychologist St. Hall in the early 20th century. A few decades later, in the 70s of the 20th century, another scientist K. Kenniston marked a new period in the life of young people, starting after adolescence and continuing until entering “adult” life. This period was called youthful, but later, due to the presence of similar problems in adolescents and young men associated with socialization during "adult" life, the concept of "youth" expanded its meaning, combining both periods and denoting what is today known as "youth culture".

The integration of young men and adolescents into a single youth culture indicates that these age groups have common social characteristics, the leading of which is a common social status in terms of roles performed in society. Other common characteristics that unite adolescents and young men in youth culture are psychological and cultural.

The cultural qualities of youth are manifested in the presence of representatives of specific interests, values, attitudes and beliefs, special ideas about the world

and the lifestyle associated with them, as well as the desire to oppose their world to the world of adults.

In connection with the isolation of young people into a separate socio-demographic group in foreign literature on sociology there have been two main approaches to its study, somehow: the functionalist approach and the theory of subcultures. Initially, in the 1940s and 60s, works on the sociology of youth were dominated by functionalist approach, which was developed mainly by American scientists - T. Parsons and his followers. According to this approach, the emergence of youth culture in a modern industrial society is associated with a prolongation of the transition period from childhood to adulthood and is aimed at the adaptation and integration of young people into the adult world. In accordance with this, the functions of youth culture were also determined:

- positive adaptation in society;
- assignment of primary status;
- facilitating emancipation from parents;
- transfer of specific values and ideas and so on.

The important components of the communicative character of the youth subculture is slang, which happens and functions in the linguistic personality of the teenager as a result of his involvement in activities youth subculture. Slang is an opposed language to the literary one. There are two types of slang in linguistics. The general slang includes words and phrases that are recognizable and used within several subcultures and the special slang consists of words and phrases that function within individual subcultures. Slang is used in youth subcultures to express subculturally important ideals verbally and acts as a thesaurus or dictionary for the subculture. The reflection of subculturally significant values in slang indicates its strong ties with units of the cognitive level and, therefore, it can be used in the reconstruction of a teenager's linguistic personality as a representative of a subcultural association through the use of a frame approach in the organization of slang vocabulary used in the youth subculture.

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